

**A Reliability Generalization Meta-analysis of the reduced
Morningness–Eveningness Questionnaire regarding Internal Consistency
(working title)**

Circadian preference has been of interest across various research fields and use cases. For its assessment, the reduced Morningness-Eveningness Questionnaire (rMEQ) is commonly used. While its brief composition of five items makes it practical, it also raises questions about its reliability across diverse populations and contexts. This study will perform a reliability generalization meta-analysis aimed at estimating the internal consistency of the rMEQ, using Cronbach's alpha. Eligible records will include peer-reviewed papers citing the rMEQ and reporting Cronbach's alpha, published from 1991 onward. Literature searches will be conducted via the OVID platform (covering ERIC, PsycINFO, and MEDLINE) and Web of Science. A random-effects model will be applied to estimate average reliability coefficients, and meta-regression will be used to examine potential moderators.

Introduction

While some people prefer to engage in most of their activities in the early morning, others prefer later hours. This phenomenon is referred to in chronobiology as circadian preference (Horne & Östberg, 1977). In contrast to chronotype, which captures actual behavior, circadian preference focuses on the individual's preference (Bauduco et al., 2020; Roenneberg et al., 2003). Although the labels have sometimes been used inconsistently, confused across some fields of research and separation is not always clear (Bauduco et al., 2020).

Regarding circadian preference, three types are commonly distinguished: the Morning type that prefers early rising and performing tasks in the earlier day vs the Evening type which prefers later hours. In the middle is the intermediate type which prefers neither strongly (Horne & Östberg, 1976; 1977). In the population, circadian

preference follows a gaussian distribution, with morning and evening types each representing approximately 10 % of the population, while the intermediate type comprises about 80% (Ashkenazi et al., 1997).

It has been discussed whether morningness and eveningness represent two independent dimensions or opposite ends of a continuum (Neubauer, 1992), with supporting evidence for both the first (Preckel et al., 2020) and the latter view (Natale & Cicogna, 2002).

Circadian preference has been linked to a series of psychological variables; particularly sleep-related variables like wake-up time, total sleep duration, and sleep quality (Gianotti et al., 2002; Soehner et al., 2011). Associations extend beyond sleep, covering areas such as academic achievement, personality traits, and mental as well as physical health (Cheung et al., 2023; Makarem et al., 2020; Tonetti et al., 2015; Tsausis, 2010).

Over the years, a variety of tests have been developed (f.e. MES; Smith et al., 1989; the preference scale: Smith et al., 2002), the first being the Morningness Eveningness Questionnaire (MEQ) by Horne and Östberg (1976). The 19 item self report questionnaire has been used in a variety of contexts (Di Milla et al, 2013). Since it has been criticised to not only capture circadian preference (Larsen, 1985; Neubauer, 1992), and a shorter version is more time and cost efficient, a reduced version has been developed by Adan and Amirall (1991): the reduced Morningness-Eveningness Questionnaire (rMEQ).

The reduced Morningness-Eveningness-Questionnaire

The rMEQ consists of 5 items (items 1, 5, 7, 10, and 18 of the original MEQ). In three items, participants indicate their preferred time on a timeline, which is then scored from 1 to 5. One item assesses morning tiredness on a 4-point scale. Lastly, participants estimate their chronotype (definitely morning, rather morning, rather evening, definitely evening), scored as 6, 4, 2, or 0, respectively. The total score

reached can vary between 4 and 25. Based on the total score five subgroups are defined: Definitely Evening Type (4-7), Moderately Evening Type (8-11), Neither /Intermediate Type (12-17), Moderately Morning Type (18-21) and Definitely Morning Type (22-25).

Since its publication, the rMEQ has been widely used across research domains (Di Milla et al., 2013) and has been translated into multiple language versions (e.g. Carciofo et al., 2013; Rahafar et al., 2015; Sinha et al., 2024). The scores of the rMEQ correlate closely with those of the original MEQ (Adan & Almirall, 1991), and several studies have focused on showing the validity of the rMEQ mostly focussing on external validity (e.g. Carciofo et al., 2012; Natale et al., 2006; Rahafar et al., 2015).

While there have been psychometric studies about the new language versions (see above) and a narrative review about Circadian preference tools including the rMEQ (Di Milla et al., 2013), no meta-analytic work on its reliability exists to date. Given its wide use and short composition, it is crucial to systematically investigate the reliability of the rMEQ across different research contexts and use cases.

Reliability and Generalisation Meta Analyses

Reliability is crucial for the trustworthiness of an instrument across different studies (Rodriguez & Meada, 2006). Even if a test reached sufficient reliability in the original construction sample, its reliability may differ in the field due to sample characteristics or differences in test administration (Jahrami et al., 2025; Tavakol & Dennick, 2011; Vacha-Haase, 1998).

To analyse a test's reliability systematically, a Reliability Generalization Meta Analysis (REGEMA) is the method of choice (Sanchez- Meca et al., 2021). It performs a meta-analysis using the reported reliability coefficients as outcomes. This approach enables a more accurate estimate of reliability and opens the possibility of moderator analyses to identify potential factors influencing reliability (Vacha-Haase, 1998).

A best-practice checklist for reporting REGEMAs has been proposed by Sanchez-Meca et al. (2021).

Aim/Objectives

The first aim of this REGEMA is to obtain a better estimation of the average reliability of the rMEQ measures.

Secondly it is to investigate whether there is heterogeneity in the reliability of the rMEQ scale used and to identify potential moderators influencing it.

Potential Moderators

The potential moderators are organised based on the suggested extraction criteria proposed by Sanchez-Meca and colleagues (2021).

Mean test score: Tests are ideally designed to measure the intended construct reliably across the entire trait continuum. However, samples with extreme mean scores might be more homogeneous, which could result in lower internal consistency (Pike & Hudson, 1998). Therefore, it will be examined whether the mean rMEQ score affects the reported reliability.

In the following moderators concerning sample characteristics will be described.

Gender: Findings concerning whether circadian preference and its distribution differs significantly between genders are inconsistent. Some studies report significant differences (Adan & Natale, 2002; Caci et al., 2009; Randler, 2011), whereas others show opposite or mixed results (Diaz-Morales & Sorroche, 2008; Randler & Engelke, 2019; Tankova et al., 1994). Given this inconsistency, it is of interest to investigate whether the rMEQ measures circadian preference with comparable reliability across genders. If genders differ in their homogeneity regarding circadian preference this may influence the internal consistency.

Age: Age is positively correlated with morningness, such that older individuals tend to score higher (Caci et al., 2009, Randler, 2019). It can be hypothesised that the

rMEQ's reliability might vary across age groups. Specifically, more homogeneous extreme groups (potentially older adults) could show different reliability patterns compared to more heterogeneous groups, based on lower variances influencing reliability estimates (Pike & Hudson, 1998).

Life stage: This moderator describes the life phase of participants, such as being in school, university, work life or retirement. Individuals in school or work settings may be less flexible in creating their daily schedules and influenced more by social *Zeitgeber*n (DiMilla, 2005; Mecacci & Zani, 1983) resulting in a lower variability in their answers. Some items may be perceived less relevant by them due to them being used to their schedules made by those environmental and social influences. University students may have more possibilities to create their own schedule, try different times of activities and therefore might show a higher variability in their answers. This could lead to a higher reliability for university students compared to individuals in work settings.

Shift work: Shift work has been linked to disturbances in circadian rhythms (Bolvin & Boudreau, 2014). Shift workers might interpret or respond to time-related items differently, potentially altering item intercorrelations. Furthermore, the full version of the MEQ has been criticised for showing a low sensitivity in shift or night work populations, while being reliable for day time workers (Adan & Almirall, 1991). Therefore it could be hypothesised that the rMEQ shows a similar pattern.

Clinical sample: Given that the rMEQ is used across both clinical and non-clinical populations, it is relevant to explore whether clinical samples exhibit different reliability coefficients.

Additionally moderators related to test version will be considered.

Language version: The rMEQ has been translated into various languages (e.g. Carciofo et al., 2012; Jankowski, 2013; Rahafar et al., 2015; Sinha et al., 2024). Translating items can alter the semantic interpretation of instruments. Perceiving items as more or less similar to each other can influence answer patterns leading to an

altered inter item correlation and accordingly the internal consistency. Therefore, it is important to investigate whether the language version or the country of test administration moderates the reported reliability coefficients.

Test version: Different test versions and lengths might result in different reliabilities. It can be assumed that a shorter test length will result in lower reliability estimates (Schmitt, 1996).

Test administration: It will be recorded whether the rMEQ was administered via paper-pencil, online format or interview. It has been shown that using an online version does not necessarily, but potentially can alter a test's psychometrics (Buchanan et al., 2005; Naus et al., 2005). Additionally administering the test via an interview instead of self administered can change response behaviour (Bowling, 2005). Accordingly it will be tested whether the reliability changes in online-administrations or interviews compared to paper-pencil settings.

Item randomisation: This assesses whether the rMEQ items were presented in the original order or randomised. Since randomisation could reduce carry-over effects (Tourangeau et al., 1989), it might impact the internal consistency of the test.

Moderators related to methods include the following.

Study type: This moderator captures whether the study was primarily psychometric or experimental/correlational in nature. Psychometric studies work with a more standardised and controlled setting and might therefore produce more homogenous reliability coefficients compared to field use. Many studies refer to the reliability reported in psychometric studies instead of reporting their own. Following it is especially interesting to test whether the reliability differs between psychometric and field studies.

Manipulation: This moderator refers to whether the study included interventions such as sleep training. Such manipulations might influence test results and,

consequently, affect variances and item correlations resulting in different reliability estimates.

Furthermore extrinsic characteristics will be regarded as potential moderators.

Year of publication: Differences between older and more recent studies may also impact reliability estimates, potentially reflecting improvements in methodology or changes in sample characteristics over time.

Research field: The rMEQ is used across various research fields (Di Milla et al, 2013). The context might influence its reliability.

Methods

Selection criteria

To be included a report needs to: a) use the rMEQ. b) All language adaptations of this test are included. c) Only reports published after 1991 will be considered, since this is the rMEQ's year of publication. d) Papers written in any language will be included. For reports not written in English, German or French, a translation tool will be used. e) Only peer-reviewed journal articles and dissertations will be included. Books and systematic reviews will be excluded. f) To be suitable a study has to report the reliability estimate for their specific sample or offer sufficient data to calculate it. g) This REGEMA will focus on the internal consistency reported with Cronbach's Alpha. All types of populations will be included, and population characteristics like clinical background or life stage will be used as moderators.

Search Strategy

Reports will be identified through database searches. The OVID platform will be used to search ERIC, PsycINFO, and MEDLINE. Additionally, the Web of Science database will be used. In those databases a forward search approach will be used. All entries that cite the original version of the rMEQ will be extracted. Databases like EconBiz, PSYNDEX or Pub Med that do not allow for forward search were assessed, but seemed to show no additional value to the databases already included.

All identified records will be imported into a Mendeley library, and duplicates will be removed. The remaining reports will then be uploaded into the screening tool Rayyan (Ouzzani et al., 2016) for abstract and full-text screening.

In the abstract screening, reports will be included if they are published after 1991 and journal articles or dissertations. Books and systematic reviews will be excluded (see eligibility criteria c) and e)). Study protocols will be traced to their final publications where possible. Reports without retrievable abstracts will be excluded.

During full-text screening, studies must meet all previously outlined eligibility criteria.

To ensure reliability and quality, a second reviewer will independently screen a subset of studies. Interrater reliability will be reported using Krippendorff's Alpha.

Data Extraction

The coding scheme will be based on the Open Psych CAMA template (Burgard et al., 2021), covering four levels: report, study, sample, and outcome.

On report level full study title, all authors and APA citation will be extracted. On study level year and country of data collection, study design, and research field will be coded. For experimental studies, it will also be coded whether the manipulation was sleep-related. On sample level the target population, mean and standard deviation of age, gender distribution, and the presence of shift work will be coded. Additionally it will be coded whether it is a clinical sample and which lifestage the participants are in (school, studies, work retirement, unemployment). On outcome level the raw Cronbach's Alpha value, mean and standard deviation of rMEQ scores and sample size will be extracted. Furthermore, it will be noted whether all five rMEQ items were used, whether items were randomized, the administration mode (online vs. paper-pencil), and the language version of the test.

An overview will be provided concerning how many of the studies using the rMEQ impute the reliability referring to those achieved psychometric studies, comment on reliability or do not mention it at all.

All information will initially be coded by a primary coder. To ensure reliability, a second coder will code a subset of the papers, and interrater agreement will again be reported using Krippendorff's Alpha. All disagreements will be discussed.

3. Planned analyses

Statistical model

The analyses will be performed using the metafor package (Viechtbauer, 2010) in the free statistical software R (R core team, 2023). A random-effects model will be applied, assuming the reliability estimates do not only vary due to sampling error but come from a distribution of reliability estimates. This reflects the circumstances better and is to be preferred above OLS or fixed effects models, following the recommendations from Lopez-Ibanez and colleagues (2024). The effects will be weighed on the inverse variance.

The heterogeneity will be assessed using the Q statistic and I^2 index.

Moderator analysis

Meta-regressions will be conducted to assess potential moderators. First, each moderator will be tested individually. Subsequently, multiple moderators will be combined based on the amount of heterogeneity they explain and their intercorrelations, in order to avoid multicollinearity.

Sensitivity analyses

A potential publication bias will be assessed using a funnel plot and Egger's regression test for funnel asymmetry (Egger et al., 1997). Additionally, influence analyses will be performed using the influence functions from the metafor package (Viechtbauer, 2010), with particular focus on Cook's distances and studentized residuals. If detected the analysis will be run again without the overly influential cases.

All analyses will be once performed with the raw alpha coefficients. Additionally the analyses will be rerun using Bonett Transformation (Bonett, 2002) and Hakistan and Whalen's (HW) Transformation (Hakistan & Whalen, 1976).

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